

DMP: Activities affecting CO2 emission in EU Countries

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Type: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Title: Activities affecting CO2 emission in EU Countries

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1 DATA DESCRIPTION AND COLLECTION OR RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

1a How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

- We collected the data made available for public use by DataHub.io which provide insights into data about the EU emission trading system (ETS). The EU emission trading system (ETS) is one of the main measures introduced by the EU to achieve cost-efficient reductions of greenhouse gas emissions and reach its targets under the Kyoto Protocol and other commitments. The second set of data also comes from DataHub.io and gives a comprehensive country code information, including ISO 3166 codes, ITU dialing codes, ISO 4217 currency codes, and many other information. The data was fetched using R in RStudio with the support of the readr library which helped read the data into the software.

1b What data will be collected or produced?

- The data we are fetching are stored in a .csv format. The datatypes we are inspecting are mainly textual data: include data that is primarily composed of written text, and numeric data: include data that is quantitative in nature. The data format is Comma-Separated Values (CSV), which is a simple format used to store tabular data, such as spreadsheets or databases. Each row of the CSV file represents a record, and each column represents a field of that record. CSV is a plain text format, which means that it can be easily read and edited using any text editor or spreadsheet software. Each record is represented as a single line, and the values in each column are separated by a comma. The first line of the file contains the names of the columns. In this experiment one of the datasets used is 127 kilobytes (kB) in size and contains 250 rows and 56 columns, and the other one is 871 kilobytes (kB) in size and containf 41915 row and 8 columns.

2 DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY

2a What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

- For the datasets I am working with, the following metadata and documentation will be provided:
 1. Metadata: A metadata file will be provided along with the datasets, which will include information about the title, author, description, keywords, file format, and data sources.

2. Organization of data: The datasets will be organized in separate folders within the project directory. Each dataset will have a separate folder, and within each folder, the data files will be organized based on their respective data types. For example, all the csv files will be kept together and all the images will be kept together.
3. Documentation for re-use: The datasets will come with a detailed documentation file that will include information on the methodology used for data collection, data cleaning and preprocessing steps, variable definitions, units of measurement, and any other relevant information that is necessary for reusing the data.
4. Capturing and recording information: The information will be captured and recorded in multiple ways, including file headers, readme files, and codebooks. The codebooks will contain information about the variables in the dataset, including their descriptions, values, and units of measurement. The readme file will contain general information about the project, including the purpose of the project, the sources of data, and any other relevant information. The file headers will contain information about the data files themselves, including their formats and the date of creation/modification.

2b What data quality control measures will be used?

- To ensure the consistency and quality of data in my project, I will implement the following data quality control measures:
 1. Standardized data collection: The data will be collected using a standardized data collection form to ensure consistency in the format of the data.
 2. Data entry validation: Before data is entered into the system, I will set up data entry validation rules to identify and flag any data that does not meet the pre-defined validation criteria.
 3. Peer review of data: To ensure the accuracy of the data, I will have a peer review process in place where another member of my team will review and validate the data.
 4. Use of controlled vocabularies: I will use controlled vocabularies or standardized classifications for any data that involves subjective interpretation, to ensure consistency and accuracy across the data.
 5. Data cleaning: Before analysis, I will clean the data by identifying and resolving inconsistencies, duplications, and errors. I will document all the steps taken during data cleaning and make this information available to others who may need to use the data.

By implementing these measures, I will ensure that my data is consistent, accurate, and of high quality, which will improve its value and usefulness for future research.

3 STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING THE RESEARCH PROCESS

3a How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

- For storage and backup during the research process, I recommend that you store the data in a robust and managed storage system with automatic backup, such as the IT support services provided by your home institution. It is also recommended to store the data in at least two separate locations to ensure that it is protected in case of any unexpected incidents.

3b How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

- To ensure data security and protection of sensitive data during the research, it should carefully be considered who will have access to the data and how access will be controlled, especially in collaborative partnerships. It is important to comply with institutional data protection policies that are in place and to take

measures to protect sensitive data, such as personal data, politically sensitive information, or trade secrets. In the event of an incident, you should have a plan in place to recover the data, and it should be regularly reviewed and updated as necessary. It is also important to identify the main risks to the data and to take measures to manage them, such as encrypting the data, using secure passwords, and limiting access to authorized people only.

4 LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS, CODES OF CONDUCT

4a If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

- Based on the license descriptions of the datasets we are using, personal data is NOT being processed. Therefore, compliance with legislation on personal data and security may not be applicable in this case.

4b How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

- For the first dataset, which is based on ISO and other standards bodies, the maintainers have released the dataset into the public domain, there may be partial restrictions on further use and reuse of the data due to the original sources' rights and licensing policies. ISO makes the list of alpha-2 country codes available for internal use and non-commercial purposes free of charge, which implies that other uses may not be permitted. Therefore, in the future it is important to check the original sources for any specific restrictions, especially if the data will be used in a public or commercial product.
- For the second dataset, which is sourced from the European Environment Agency, no copyright restrictions are applied. The agency promotes the sharing of environmental data and requires data providers to have assurance that their data are properly handled, disseminated, and acknowledged following similar principles and rules across countries and stakeholders. Regarding ethical issues and codes of conduct, it is important to follow national and international codes of conduct and institutional ethical guidelines. Any ethical issues that may affect how data are stored and transferred, who can see or use them, and how long they are kept should be considered and planned for accordingly. If data collection in the research project requires ethical review, it is important to obtain it from an ethics committee.

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5a How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

- The data will be shared via two platforms: Orcid and Zenodo. Orcid is a global, interdisciplinary directory of researchers and research organizations. Zenodo is a digital repository that enables researchers to share, preserve, and cite research data and other digital artifacts. Both platforms are trustworthy data repositories, indexed in catalogues, and use secure data services to handle data requests. There are no restrictions to data sharing, and there are no embargo reasons mentioned. The data will be made available immediately after deposition on Zenodo, which is a platform for open access and immediate sharing of data. There is no exclusive use of the data claimed, and there is no mention of postponing or restricting data sharing for any reasons. The data will be accessible to anyone with access to Data Stewardship 2023 – DMPs community on Zenodo and Orcid . There are no restrictions to data access or sharing mentioned, and no data sharing agreements are required or mentioned. Therefore, no action is needed to overcome or minimize restrictions.

5b How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

- The data to be retained will be all the raw data collected during the project, including experimental data, and any other relevant data that can be used for future research purposes. The foreseeable research uses for the data include the replication of the experiments conducted in this project, further analysis, and integration with other data sources to derive new insights and knowledge. The data will be deposited in Zenodo. The data will be preserved for a minimum of one year after the project's completion. There are no contractual, legal, or regulatory requirements for data retention or destruction, and all the data collected during the project will be preserved. Metadata curation services to ensure the data's discoverability and usability for future research purposes.

5c What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

- Users can access the data directly from these repositories using a web browser or by downloading the data and loading it into R or another analysis tool. Potential users will need to have R and the necessary libraries installed in order to access and use the data. It may also be helpful for users to have some basic knowledge of R programming.

5d How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

- We plan to deposit the data in a trustworthy data repository such as Zenodo, which will automatically generate a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for our dataset upon submission. This DOI will provide a persistent identifier for our data, ensuring that it can be reliably located and referred to by other researchers. We will ensure that the DOI is included in any publications or other outputs that result from our research.

6 DATA MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6a Who will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

- As this is an individual project, there are no partners to coordinate data management responsibilities with. I will be responsible for implementing the DMP and ensuring it is regularly reviewed and updated as necessary. It is important to keep the DMP up-to-date to reflect any changes in the project and data management processes.

6b What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

- Since this project is part of the course Data Stewardship with the Data Science Program in TU Vienna we are unable to estimate any cost.